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Journal:	<i>Wind Energy</i>
Manuscript ID	WE-17-0054.R1
Wiley - Manuscript type:	Research Article
Date Submitted by the Author:	30-Jul-2017
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Keywords:	Wind Energy, Variability, Electricity, Planning, MVP, Europe

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Using wind velocity estimated from a reanalysis to minimize the variability of aggregated wind farm production over Europe.

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Abstract

In this work we use the mean-variance portfolio (MVP) optimization, using as input the power derived from the wind and density results of meteorological model simulations (ERA-Interim reanalysis), to minimize the variability of the wind power produced in a large region. The methodology involves selecting the placement of the wind farms on a high-spatial-resolution grid. We used the EU-28 region to check the method and perform sensitivity tests. We studied the influence of the ratio between the total installed power of the whole domain (P_t) and the maximum power that can be installed per cell (P_{mi}) on the variability of wind power yield. The results show that the reliability of the electrical system improves when P_{mi} grows and worsens when P_t grows. It was found that a quadratic fit relates the variability of the system and the aforementioned ratio. The optimization procedure tends to select groups of terrain cells where wind farms should be installed. These groups grow when more energy production is demanded of the system, but they roughly maintain their location. There is some evidence that in a larger region greater system reliability could be achieved. Most of the selected cells have either a high or a low capacity factor and those with the latter are crucial in enhancing system reliability.

Keywords

Wind Energy; Variability; Electricity; Planning; MVP; Europe

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Introduction

In many countries, there has been a rapid development of wind energy. While a small amount of wind energy can be incorporated into the electrical system without difficulty, higher amounts of it generate problems in predicting how much energy has to be produced by other sources, mainly coal, oil, open-cycle gas turbines, combined-cycle gas turbines, combustible renewables and waste, and hydro power [1]. In addition, other undesirable consequences, such as difficulties for the grid or increased costs of secondary services, have already been identified and estimated [2, 3, 4]. While wind power prediction, mainly based on persistence and atmospheric models' predictions, helps in ameliorating the problem, a non-negligible degree of uncertainty about the wind power that will be added to the electrical system still exists. It leads to instabilities in the electrical network and therefore limits the number of wind farms that it is desirable to have installed in a region. In order to compensate for that instability, a number of flexible resources (e.g. dispatchable power plants, demand-side management, etc.) whose power output should be equal to the variability are required to cover it [5]. Therefore, to increase the amount of clean energy from wind power that is provided to the electrical network, either the number of flexible resources must also grow or the wind power variability must be reduced. The installation and maintenance of flexible resources increases the overall cost of energy. From the work of Roques et al. [6] and Drake and Hubacek [7], we know that variability of wind energy can be reduced by combining the power output of separate wind farms or countries in a powerful electrical grid such as an HVDC (high-voltage direct current) grid. This would ensure an electricity supply when lack of wind in a region causes a decrease in energy produced, by transporting it with small losses from regions where at the same time an excess is being generated. To achieve that, these studies, as well as ours, use the mean-variance portfolio (MVP) theory, based on Markowitz's seminal work [8]. They also show that a curve exists that relates the minimum achievable variability in wind energy produced to the average capacity factor of all the wind farms.

Roques et al. [6] used as an input of the MVP methodology the power generated by five European countries (Spain, France, Germany, Denmark and Austria), and for each average capacity factor they calculated the share of power that should be installed in each country to optimize the system from the variability point of view. The authors concluded that, although constraints exist that cause the reality to diverge from the theoretical results, there is room for renewable energies policies in Europe to bring the reality closer to the optimal reliability derived from their study. From a more strictly scientific point of

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2 view, their work leaves open aspects such as the possible extension of the method to a region closer to
3 where the European policies apply, or the spatial and temporal details of the data used. These two
4 issues, among others, are those that the present work intends to address. Prior to the work cited above,
5 Drake and Hubacek [7] considered four wind farms in England and they used MVP theory with hourly
6 power generation figures to calculate the optimal geographical distribution of a fixed installed power.
7 According to their findings, a significant reduction in the variability of wind generation is expected
8 from dispersion of wind farms. Following the methodology of the aforementioned studies, in this study
9 we propose to take the output of meteorological models as the input and calculate an optimal
10 distribution of wind farms in the model mesh. This has the advantage of being capable of achieving a
11 higher spatial resolution than Roques et al.'s approach [6]. It also has the advantage over Drake and
12 Hubacek's approach [7] of making it possible to estimate wind power in places where no
13 measurements are available. This approach allows the use of meteorological models to plan a network
14 of wind farms that minimizes the overall variability of the power that they produce as a whole. Some
15 other works have also used the MVP methodology to minimize the variability of wind power
16 production, such as Hansen [9], who investigated the interconnection of three wind farms in the United
17 States of America; Degeilh and Singh [10], who optimized the location of wind farms using the sites of
18 the National Renewable Energy Laboratory wind database; Rombauts et al. [11], who delved into the
19 study conducted by Roques et al. [6] for five European countries; and Novacheck and Johnson [12],
20 who evaluated the potential of diversification of wind power generation sites to reduce the variability
21 of this energy source in the United States Midwest. Thomaidis et al. [13] recently used the MVP
22 methodology to study the optimal geographic distribution of wind farms and solar concentrating
23 facilities in the south of the Iberian peninsula, concluding that, at least in this context, policies that take
24 energy mix into consideration will have a clear advantage over those that favour the profit of individual
25 sites.

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46 In the present work, the MVP methodology is also used, but to investigate the variability of wind
47 energy production for the European Union as a whole; also, there is a wide choice of locations for the
48 wind farms thanks to the great spatial detail afforded by the use of data drawn from reanalysis.

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53 Giebel et al. [14] showed that the electrical losses incurred by transporting energy harvested in Egypt to
54 Europe would be compensated for economically by the large differences in wind resources. Czisch and
55 Giebel [15] and Czisch [16] proved that transporting electricity is one of the keys to an economical
56 electricity supply in a 100% renewable scenario. They also showed that in such a scenario transmission
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2 losses would add up to 4.2% of the energy produced using an HVDC grid on top of the existing high-
3 voltage grid. We will assume the existence, across the domain, of an efficient electrical grid whose
4 transmission losses would be of the same value – that is, 4.2%. However, this maximum could be
5 lower, since Novacheck and Johnson [12] pointed out that in an electrical network with low variability,
6 there would be reductions in network congestion, which would result in lower losses due to transport.
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12 We will apply this methodology in the EU-28 domain – first without any land use restrictions, and then
13 increasing the land use restrictions to assess their impact on the variability. We will also study the
14 impact of increasing the average capacity factor. After applying this methodology in the EU-28 domain
15 to check its viability, we will draw some conclusions about mid- and long-term planning of the wind
16 power system in Europe.
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22 Methodology

23 **a) Wind data**

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25 To estimate the wind resources across EU-28 we used ERA-Interim reanalysis. The wind obtained
26 from that compilation was computed using a four-dimensional variational analysis using the version
27 Cy31r2 of the IFS model from ECMWF [17]. It provided analysis four times a day: at 00:00, 06:00,
28 12:00, and 18:00 UTC. Although the reanalysis period starts in 1979, we had to use data from a time
29 span of 10 years because of limitations in computer power. We chose the last 10 available years (2004
30 to 2013) from the time that this study started. The data were extracted for Europe at the maximum
31 available spatial resolution, 0.25×0.25 degrees, which results in cells of approximately 550 km^2 . We
32 gained time series of 14,612 data for each cell, which gave us a good sample of their wind regime.
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44 For our experiment we selected all the land cells of the EU-28 territory. In addition, we selected some
45 offshore cells: those with depths of less than 50 m and no more than 100 km from the coast. Although
46 some advances in maximum sea depth achievable in the installation of wind turbines have been made
47 in recent years, the distance from the coast remains the key limiting factor because the installation,
48 exploitation and maintenance costs grow with it. We discarded sea cells at a distance greater than three
49 cells from the shore (approximately 100 km), which is within the range of available technology and
50 management (e.g. Cradden et al. [18]). This limit is approximately equal to the limit employed in other
51 studies (e.g. Lu et al. [19] and Musial and Butterfield [20]). All these restrictions result in the map
52 given in figure 1.
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4 To obtain the power generated from the wind, we chose a G90 2 MW Gamesa wind turbine with a hub
5 height of 100 m, because it is a medium-power turbine that can be installed offshore or inland. To
6 transform wind and density data to power, we used its power curve, rated for an air density of
7 1.225 kg/m³, and corrected the output power by normalizing it for air density, as IEC (International
8 Electrotechnical Commission) power performance standards recommend [21]. This is done by
9 modifying the wind speed that is fed to the power curve as follows:
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$$V_{\text{norm}} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{r}{r_0}} V_{\text{orig}} \quad (1)$$

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23 We used the same turbine at the same height for land and sea cells, because we did not want to
24 introduce variability in the selection of turbines.
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28 The wind speed and density at a height of 100 m were calculated by interpolating from the eta levels of
29 the Era-Interim dataset. To achieve this, we iteratively applied the barometric law to transform the
30 time-dependent pressure and temperature of each level to height in metres over the surface. Afterwards,
31 the wind speed and density were interpolated to a fixed height of 100 m over the model's surface. We
32 used a monotone piecewise cubic algorithm [22] to prevent the overshooting that can occur in the
33 interpolation with normal cubic splines.
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40 Dividing the output power by the maximum-rated power of the wind turbine at each time step, we
41 obtained the instantaneous capacity factor (CF) of each cell. This gross CF has some losses from wake
42 losses; electric losses up to the point where the electricity fed into the grid is measured; and production
43 losses due to the mechanical availability of the wind turbine generators. Although Colmenar-Santos et
44 al. [23] showed that the losses depend on the wind regime, for the present study we assumed losses of
45 2.5% [23] of the generated energy.
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53 Afterwards, the averaged CF and its standard deviation over the complete temporal series were
54 calculated for each cell. The time correlation of CF between cells was also computed. These two
55 figures were entered into the calculations for the optimization explained in the following section.
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b) Mean-variance portfolio (MVP) theory

MVP theory was initially developed for financial securities and has found wide applications in financial services. It is a methodology that seeks to minimize the risk associated with a desired return. The same procedure has been applied to calculate the share of power that should be installed in some European countries [6] or some wind farms within a single country [7]. The share of power was the result of an optimization of the trade-off between minimizing the uncertainty of the wind power generated for an electrical network and maximizing the wind power output.

In our case, the analysed region was divided into cells of regular size and in each cell we sought the fraction of the total wind power that we had to install to minimize the standard deviation of the six-hourly time series of the aggregated wind energy produced over the whole region. In other words, for each spatial distribution of wind farms, there is a time variation of the total wind power that will be produced in EU-28 over the years. We computed what this distribution should be in order to minimize that variability. In addition to the production efficiency of each cell (CF) and the cross-correlation between cells of the generated wind power, the optimum distribution of wind farms depends on certain optional factors such as the total amount of installed power, the maximum power that may be installed in each cell and the mean production efficiency (mean CF of the grid) to be reached. The sensitivity of the results to these parameters was studied.

The MVP methodology involves the calculation of the minimum standard deviation of the total energy produced from all the wind farms over the whole region. It is given by

$$\sigma_T^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N X_i^2 \sigma_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N X_i X_j \rho_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j \quad (2)$$

where

- X_i is the fraction of wind turbines that are installed in cell i ,
- σ_i is the standard deviation of the instantaneous CF of cell i , and
- ρ_{ij} is the correlation between the instantaneous CF of cell i with cell j .

under the restrictions

$$\sum_{i=1}^N X_i = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$0 < X_i < P_{mi}/P_t \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N X_i cp_i = Cp_M \quad (5)$$

where

- P_t is the total power installed in the grid,
- P_{mi} is the maximum power that may be installed in the cell i ,
- cp_i is the CF of cell i , and
- Cp_M is the mean CF of the grid.

c) Suitable values for parameters

The CF is usually in the range 30%–45% for offshore wind farms and in the range 15%–45% for onshore ones. The average CF for European wind farms in the period 2003–2007 was 0.21 [23]. For this study, given that in this period the vast majority of the European wind farms were onshore and that we expect offshore wind farms to grow more than onshore ones, we considered it reasonable to choose 0.23 as the desired mean CF of the grid. To assess the dependence of the variability with respect to this parameter, it was later increased to 0.28.

We assumed that all the cells would have the same limit on installed power (P_{mi} equal for all cells), in order to find how dependent on it the optimal variability was. To choose reasonable values of that maximum, we made the following assumptions. First, the maximum percentage of the area of a cell that could be used for installation of wind turbines was about 4%. Later in this work, this limit was increased to perform a sensitivity test that involves this factor. This limit is far lower than the one normally used for wind farms in the sea [9]. Inside this area, a distance between turbines of four or five times the rotor diameter was considered. That resulted in a maximum of approximately 250 MW for each cell (P_{mi}).

As for the total power installed in the grid (P_T), we initially used 120 GW, which is approximately the level of wind power installed in Europe in 2013 (117.289 GW) [23].

Results and discussion

a) Optimization with total installed power of 120 GW

In figure 2, a map with the time-averaged CF calculated for this work is shown. In this figure it can be observed that most wind resources are found on Europe's northern coast, especially offshore, where CFs of up to 0.60 are reached. In the south of Europe and the regions with high mountains, such as the Alps, lower CFs are found. The greater the CF of a location, the more profitable its wind farms are in general. Nevertheless, Roques et al. [6] and Drake and Hubacek [7] showed that increasing C_{pM} normally also increases the variability of the wind energy produced. We found the same trend in our results at a later stage, when the MVP methodology was applied throughout the EU-28, parcelled into 10,855 cells of about 500 km². In recent years, several studies have found similar results with methodologies other than the MVP in intermediate or small power systems – for example, Koivisto et al. [24] for the Nordic and Baltic countries.

First, the results for $P_t = 120$ GW, $P_{mi} = 250$ MW and average CF = 0.23 are shown in figure 3a, where the optimal wind farm distribution after MVP methodology is presented. Only those cells with a significant share of installed power in the portfolio are shown. The limit for significance is set to 2 MW because that is the power of a single wind turbine. Out of the 10,855 cells that participated in the optimization procedure, only 503 had a significant share; this is only a few more cells than the minimum possible for this configuration ($P_t/P_{mi} = 480$). This is because most of the significant cells reached the P_{mi}/P_t limit ($2.0833 \cdot 10^{-3}$, the share limit that corresponds to installation of 250 MW in a cell for a total power of 120 GW).

A level of 120 GW of installed wind capacity with a CF of 0.23 provides an average of 27.6 GW of power, about 9% of the European demand for the year 2008, the year with maximum electricity consumption to date [25]. The standard deviation given by the optimized portfolio was 0.0698. As the power derived from the optimized distribution follows a normal distribution (a Kolmogorov–Smirnov test was conducted, resulting in a p-value of 0.013), a standard deviation of 0.0698 means that 10.8 GW of wind power would be enabled on the grid with a probability of 97.7%. This implies that we would be unable to reach 10.8 GW for only 201 hours (about 8 days) per year. The wind power generated in the EU-28 region was 846 petajoules in 2013 [31]. We estimate that if the installed power in 2013 had been 120 GW instead of 117.289 GW, the power generated would have reached 865 petajoules. With

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2 the MVP-optimized distribution of wind farms for 120 GW, production would be 870 petajoules a year.
3 Therefore, it would be approximately the same, and we would be granting a minimum in the variability
4 of the wind power supply.
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9 With regard to the geographical distribution, it was found that the significant cells rarely appear
10 isolated but almost always form groups. It is also relevant that many cells are located near the domain's
11 boundary. These two results coincide with those achieved by Reichenberg et al. [26], who used a
12 completely different methodology and studied a distinct and smaller region. This gives greater
13 robustness to these results. In addition, the second of these two results is coherent because the limits of
14 the studied region are about 3,000 km apart; Giebel [1] pointed out that at distances greater than 3,000
15 km the correlation between wind regimes is random. This circumstance gives the cells at the periphery
16 of the domain an advantage in being chosen by the methodology as part of the optimal distribution.
17 Furthermore, we notice that the distances between adjacent groups of significant cells range roughly
18 from 200 to 500 km. This is less than the distance (725 km) at which Giebel [1] found an exponential
19 decay in the cross-correlation of wind energy production. Kiviluoma et al. [27] also demonstrated for
20 several power systems that the distance between wind power farms can explain the variability in wind
21 power production.
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34 A large number of cells are located in the Alps, where the CF is very low. The same happens in the
35 centre of Romania, the west and north of Greece, near Rome and in the Pyrenees. The placement of
36 wind farms in locations with low CF is not profitable from a local point of view, but if we look at the
37 region as a whole and seek the highest system reliability (for a fixed expected annual production), we
38 see that the MVP methodology selects cells of this type because of the low correlation between their
39 wind regime and that of many other parts of the domain. We verified this by taking a representative cell
40 of each group and performing the cross-correlation of the time series of wind power produced between
41 all the representatives. Of the 60 representative cells, 11 had a negative covariance with the Alps'
42 representative cell. The average of the covariance of each representative with the rest showed that the
43 representative cell of the Alps was the one whose mean reached the minimum, with a value of
44 $5.78 \cdot 10^{-4}$, much lower than the means of the other representative cells, which averaged $1.10 \cdot 10^{-2}$.
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55 We also applied the MVP methodology to obtain an optimal distribution of wind farms in EU-28,
56 excluding locations with $CF < 0.15$ but keeping all other parameters equal. The map of the new
57 domain, along with the CFs of its cells, is shown in figure 4a. These locations are normally considered
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2 unsuitable for installing wind turbines due to their low profitability from a local point of view. The
3 results show that the reliability of the electric system worsens considerably, because the standard
4 deviation increases to 0.085. Therefore, from a global point of view, the reliability of the system
5 worsens if low-CF cells are excluded. In figure 4b we observe, for this case too, that the wind farms are
6 located mainly on the frontier of the domain. In addition, there is an increase in the number of cells on
7 the Scandinavian and Iberian peninsulas and a reduction in those in the Baltic Sea.
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14 Returning to the basic scenario, in which the cells with CFs lower than 0.15 are included, it follows
15 from figure 5 that the CFs of the significant cells are distributed along all the values, but a higher
16 number of them are chosen around the values lower than 0.15 and higher than 0.35. On figure 3a, it can
17 also be seen that the number of significant cells with low CFs is bigger than the number with high CFs.
18 This is a consequence of restriction [4] and the fact that the share of each significant cell is almost
19 always equal to the share limit. In figure 5, we divide the cells by CF into three groups. This shows that
20 although most of the cells have an average CF, only 1.5% of them are selected to contribute to the
21 portfolio. We think that this is because most of them are close to the cells with the highest CFs in the
22 EU-28 domain, and, being highly correlated with them, medium-CF cells are discarded in favour of the
23 low-CF ones.
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34 From the above results, it seems reasonable that the strategy to reduce the variability of wind energy
35 production and, therefore, to increase its integration in the energy mix should take into account the
36 placement of wind farms in areas with low capacity factor but high anticorrelation with the wind
37 regimes of areas that already have many wind turbines. This could be an unexpected advantage in
38 terms of increasing the share of wind energy, because it is likely that social opposition will tend to be
39 close to saturation in regions with high wind power penetration, while the opposite will be true in
40 regions that have low wind potential and therefore few wind turbines. In addition, over recent decades,
41 much experience has been gained of how to overcome social reluctance to build renewable energy
42 facilities (e.g. Raven et al. [28]; Cohen et al. [29]; Enevoldsen and Sovacool [30]), which can help
43 projects to work better from the outset in places where actions of this kind have not been contemplated
44 until now.
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56 57 **b) Sensitivity to an increase in the average CF** 58 59 60

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2 If the value 120 GW is maintained for P_t and 250 MW for P_{mi} , but the average CF is changed to 0.28,
3 the map of the share (not shown) is very similar in the spatial distribution of the groups of cells to that
4 of the previous figure (3a). In almost every place where we found a group on the previous share we
5 also found a group on this one. The groups in the North Sea are bigger, and the groups where CF was
6 low are smaller. The groups that have a medium CF, such as in the north of Sweden, in the east of
7 Greece, in Portugal and elsewhere, found near the frontier of the domain, also grow in size. Overall,
8 most of the cells of the previous section remain, and some that had low CFs are substituted by others
9 that have high or average CFs but that are adjacent to the existing groups of cells.
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18 In this case, the grid would achieve an average power of 33.6 GW, but there is a worsening in the
19 standard deviation, which rises to 0.0827. This supports the hypothesis that the selected cells with low
20 CFs contribute positively to the reduction of the global standard deviation. As the mean has also
21 increased, we obtain more power on the grid (15.1 GW), with a probability of 97.7%, than in the
22 previous configuration. The standard deviation for this case is less than that found when low-CF cells
23 were excluded, even though we were requesting a higher CF, which can be translated to an overall
24 profitability of all the wind farms. Therefore, we obtained a more profitable and reliable wind farm
25 distribution by increasing the objective CF than if we optimized excluding low-CF cells.
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34 c) Test of sensitivity to the increase of the total power installed in the grid

35 It is expected that in the coming decades the level of **installed wind capacity** will increase. Therefore, it
36 is reasonable to perform a study of the sensitivity of the results of the MVP methodology to the total
37 **installed wind capacity**. In **table 1** we show the result of applying the MVP optimization for a fixed
38 average CF of 0.23, increasing the total installed power. It can be observed how the standard deviation
39 and the number of significant cells change as P_t grows, but P_{mi} is kept fixed. In **table 2** we observe the
40 same behaviour as P_{mi} decreases and P_t is kept fixed. This is because standard deviation and the number
41 of significant cells depend only on their ratio (P_{mi}/P_t), through restriction (4) and these two parameters
42 (P_{mi} and P_t) do not appear in other part of the methodology. In **table 2**, we also observe the impact of
43 increasing the percentage of land dedicated to wind farms on the variability and the percentage of
44 demand that can be met with the wind farms.
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55 For our test domain (EU-28), the relation between P_t and P_{mi} was found to fit the following quadratic
56 curve well:
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$$P_T/P_{mi} = 10^6 \cdot (6.9016 \cdot \sigma_T^2 - 0.8374 \cdot \sigma_T + 0.0253) \quad (6)$$

with a standard deviation for the error of the fit of 12.5.

The number of significant cells grows almost linearly with the aforementioned ratio. It is a consequence of the fact that almost all the selected cells reach the share limit in these experiments too. The geographical distribution of the significant cells for all the values of P_T (keeping P_{mi} equal to 250MW) is similar (figures 3a–3e). They differ in that the groups of cells grow when P_T grows. As the groups grow, they eventually merge with other groups. Some new groups also appear. Figure 3f shows the selected cells and their CF for P_T equal to 1,200 GW. Most of the groups of cells have grown and merged. A new group has appeared in Sicily and the south of Italy and another in the south-west of Sweden. The number of selected cells is 44.7% of the total cells of the domain.

Although the number of selected cells increases when P_T/P_{mi} grows, their geographical distribution retains some common features with the distribution for low values of P_T/P_{mi} . Essentially, the selected cells tend to group at the domain's boundary, in zones of low CF around the Alps and on the northern coast.

d) Consistency and benefits of the methodology

To quantify the improvement in the variability obtained with the method, we compared it with 100,000 randomly generated samples of wind farm distributions. For each sample, 750 of the 10,855 cells were chosen, and a random distribution was generated for them. It was modified to fulfil restrictions (3) and (5) for $C_{pM} = 0.23$, by projecting the samples into the subspace generated by them. The variability calculated with them had an average of 0.1063. That means that the instantaneous CF will fluctuate between 0.44 and 0.02 with 95.4% probability. In contrast, the optimized case with $P = 120$ GW and $P_{mi} = 250$ MW will fluctuate between 0.37 and 0.09. For the amount of wind power installed in Europe (117 GW in 2013), this would imply a difference of 16 GW of backup power.

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2 The range of values for the random variability was between 0.191 and 0.103; while applying the MVP
3 methodology for the 750 cells of each randomly chosen case, we got variability values between 0.076
4 and 0.068, far below those obtained by the random samples. Therefore, it is very difficult to obtain a
5 variability close to the optimum by chance. This result also tells us that most of the gain of applying the
6 MVP methodology can be obtained by modifying the amount of power that is installed in an already-
7 selected set of locations.
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12 The worst variability value for each group of 750 cells can also be obtained with MVP methodology,
13 by optimizing for the opposite of equation (2). The worst value ever obtained was 0.221. Therefore, the
14 random samples do not approach the maximum either; they lie, on the contrary, on a centred range
15 between the maximum and the minimum.
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22 Conclusions

23 We used MVP optimization to calculate the places where it is desirable to place wind farms in order to
24 maximize the reliability of the total wind energy supply in Europe (UE-28). The novelty of this work
25 lies in the fact that it uses as the input for the MVP methodology the power estimated from the velocity
26 and density output of meteorological model simulations, and that it is applied on a high-resolution grid
27 over a region as wide as the European Union in order to characterize its behaviour. It was found that
28 the spatial distributions of wind farms that minimized the variability of the wind power system are
29 roughly the same regardless of the amount of power that is desired in the grid and the maximum power
30 that may be installed per domain cell. The main difference is the extension of the groups of cells where
31 wind farms are installed. This behaviour is important, because it means that once power lines have been
32 installed at the selected locations there is no need to install lines to other places as the system grows. If
33 there is any need to increase the maximum current that they can withstand, civil engineering work
34 could be reused. In addition, the number of locations to install wind farms is minimized because it
35 tends to group the cells and to install in them the maximum power allowed, and, therefore, fewer power
36 lines are required.
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51 Tests of the sensitivity of the obtained variability were performed with respect to all the variables that
52 enter into the method as restrictions: the overall capacity factor, and the ratio between the total installed
53 wind capacity and the maximum power that may be installed per cell. On both variables the variability
54 increases as they are increased. A quadratic fit was found for the ratio P_T/P_{mi} , and on both variables the
55 variability increased as they were increased.
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4 If, instead of minimizing the variability, the objective is to increase the amount of guaranteed power,
5 the situation is different; although increasing CF from 0.23 to 0.28 increased the variability of the
6 supply, the amount of guaranteed power with a probability of 97.7% also grew because the mean
7 production grew more than the standard deviation. Therefore, in the range of the studied mean CF, it is
8 better to increase the mean CF if a greater amount of guaranteed power is desired, at the expense of an
9 increase in the variability.
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18 We have shown that excluding cells with low CF in the region in question increases the variability.
19 Therefore, to reduce this variability and increase system reliability, the criterion for choosing the
20 placement of the wind farms might be changed from the current one, which is based only on the local
21 profitability of the location, to one that also takes into account the stability of the electrical system as a
22 whole. As installing wind farms in places with low CF is not profitable, a different scheme of energy
23 feed-in law seems to be needed to promote the placement of wind farms in such places.
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30 The methodology tends to select cells near the boundary of the studied domain, which proves what
31 Reichenberg et al. [26] merely hypothesized in their work on the Nordic countries and Germany,
32 namely that the variability of wind power production would decrease if the region from which wind
33 farm locations are selected were expanded to all the European countries. For this reason, if the area of
34 the study is further enlarged, the variability of the system will probably decrease further. This is an
35 argument for trying to include as many countries as possible in the domain and to create a stable
36 coordinated HVDC network that connects them. Therefore, if we use HVDC lines to connect EU-28
37 with the surrounding regions, we will not only have a more profitable installation, as the results of
38 Czisch [16] and Czisch and Giebel [15] show, but we might also reduce the variability of the supply, if
39 this method is used to choose the locations.
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48 We found that it is very difficult to obtain a distribution whose variability is close to the optimal by
49 chance. Comparing with the random distributions, we also found that most of the gain can be obtained
50 by changing, according to the results of the MVP methodology, the share of installed power of existing
51 wind farms.
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57 **Further work**

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2 To reach these conclusions we made several assumptions. We used the same type of turbine for land
3 and sea cells. A more realistic study could take into account the best turbine for each cell. We think that
4 increasing the turbine height, or using larger rotors for cells with low CF, would make it possible to
5 increase the mean CF without worsening the variability. In addition, sub-grid-cell aspects can increase
6 the CF of some locations within a cell with medium-to-complex terrain, as in several zones in the Alps
7 [32]. Taking this aspect into account would lead to a dependence of the mean CF of each cell on the
8 maximum used area of it, and therefore on its P_{mi} . This issue is beyond the scope of this paper, but it
9 would be interesting to study it in further works. We have shown that increasing the usable area per cell
10 reduces the standard deviation considerably, but in this work we did not consider whether the greatest
11 percentages of cell area used in our tests (up to 40%) are feasible in all the cells. Therefore, we plan to
12 make an accurate estimation of the usable area by incorporating in our model an Eligible Area Model,
13 such as the one used by Grassi et al. [33], which would lead to a more appropriate standard deviation
14 result. Nevertheless, from the sensitivity tests performed in this paper, we expect that the resulting
15 distribution will be very similar to the present one, adding or removing cells contiguous to the existing
16 groups. Wind measurements with higher temporal resolution of the selected cells would provide
17 reliable results on the variability that could be obtained. In addition, the wind farms already installed
18 must be taken into account. Increasing the domain would very probably decrease the variability, and
19 therefore it would be very interesting to repeat the work and include the north of Africa and all of
20 Europe. It would also provide information on the variability of the selected optimal locations with the
21 expansion of the domain. In addition, it would be interesting to see how the methodology worked with
22 a smaller domain (e.g. a country).
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Or Peer Review

P_T		120GW	240GW	360GW	480GW	600GW	1,200GW
P_T/P_{mi} ratio (GW/MW)		0.48	0.96	1.44	1.92	2.4	4.8
# of significant cells		503	984	1471	1946	2450	4856
σ_T		0.0698	0.0730	0.0756	0.0778	0.0798	0.0873
% of 2008's demand met	Average	7.56%	15.1%	22.7%	30.2%	37.8%	75.6%
	With 84.1% probability	5.53%	10.9%	16.1%	21.1%	26.1%	49.9%
	With 97.7% probability	3.39%	6.38%	9.09%	11.6%	13.9%	23.1%

Table 1: Results of the optimization procedure for $Cp_M=0.23$ and $P_{mi}=250MW$ (using 4% of each cell for wind farms).

For Peer Review

P_{mi}		2.5GW	1250MW	833MW	625MW	500MW	250MW
P_T/P_{mi} ratio (GW/MW)		0.48	0.96	1.44	1.92	2.4	4.8
# of significant cells		503	984	1471	1946	2450	4856
σ_T		0.0698	0.0730	0.0756	0.0778	0.0798	0.0873
Maximum % of the cells for wind farms		40%	20%	13.3%	10%	8%	4%
% of 2008's demand met	Average	75.6%	75.6%	75.6%	75.6%	75.6%	75.6%
	With 84.1% probability	55.3%	54.3%	53.5%	52.8%	52.2%	49.9%
	With 97.7% probability	33.9%	31.9%	30.3%	29.0%	27.7%	23.1%

Table 2: Results of the optimization for $Cp_M=0.23$ and $P_t=1200$ GW for P_{mi} variable. Observe that the first 3 rows are the same as in table 1, because these results depend only on the P_{mi}/P_T ratio.

For Peer Review

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Caption : cells classification: brown (land) and orange (offshore) are cells used for the optimization procedure; blue are land cells not used since they are outside EU-28; green are sea cells not used since distant more than 100 km from the coastline; cyan are sea cells with a depth greater than 50 m

131x102mm (300 x 300 DPI)

CF estimated for each cell of the EU-28 domain

131x89mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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CF of the selected cells for mean CF=0.23 and a) 120Gw/250Mw, b) 240Gw/250Mw, c) 360Gw/250Mw, d) 480Gw/250Mw, e) 600Gw/250Mw, f) 1200Gw/250Mw Pt/Pm ratios in the domain.

112x59mm (300 x 300 DPI)

left: CF estimated for each cell of the EU-28 domain excluding cells whose CF is less than 0.15. right: for the domain on the left, the cells not chosen by the optimization procedure are grey, while the chosen ones keep their color.

71x28mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Cell distribution by CF for Pt/Pmi = 120/0.25. The total number of cells were 10855, while the selected ones were only 503 (a 4.6% of the total). Blue: percentage of the total of the cells for each category. Green: idem for the percentage of the selected cells. Brown: percentage of the power that the selected cells provide to the nework by category.

162x130mm (300 x 300 DPI)

